

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 5

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович

*PhD, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena

*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор, Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Саидов Саидмир Абборович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталю Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

PhD, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии
факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ.
Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой
акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой
диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета,
д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shaykatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Shukrullayeva G.J., Axmedov A.A.**
THE CONDITION AND FEATURES OF HARD TISSUES OF TEETH DURING PREGNANCY.....10
2. **Vokhidov E.R.**
ASSESSMENT OF DENTAL STATUS AND ORAL HEALTH IN PREGNANT WOMEN.16
3. **Kuliev O.A., Karabaev A.G.**
PATHOGENETIC BASIS OF REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DISORDERS IN THE POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD.....21

THERAPY

4. **Musayeva L.J., Yakubov A.V., Zufarov P.S., Abdusamatova D.Z., Saidova Sh.A., Pulatova N.I.**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF REBAMIPID IN THE TREATMENT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....26
5. **Yakubov A.V., Musayeva L.J., Akbarova D.S., Saidova Sh.A., Aripdjanova Sh.S., Avazova G.N.**
THE CURRENT ROLE OF MACROLYDES IN THE TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA.....31
6. **Khasanjanova F.O., Mamatova N.T.**
ASSESSMENT OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME AS AN INDEPENDENT PREDICTOR OF DISEASE PROGNOSIS.....37
7. **Makhmudova N.M.**
PHYTOTHERAPY OF DYSPEPTIC SYMPTOMS IN PATIENTS WITH H. PYLORI-ASSOCIATED CHRONIC GASTRITIS USING THE DIETARY SUPPLEMENT VENTRAP.....43

SURGERY

8. **Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Mukhiddinov B.X., Askarov P.A.**
ASSESSMENT OF RENAL DYSFUNCTION IN YOUNG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME AS AN INDEPENDENT PREDICTOR OF DISEASE PROGNOSIS.....50
9. **Makhmudov T.B., Sherbekov U.A., Kurbaniazov Z.D.**
PROGNOSTIC FACTORS FOR CHOOSING THE VOLUME OF OPERATION IN TOXIC FORMS OF GOITER.....59
10. **Makhmudov T.B., Sherbekov U.A., Kurbaniazov Z.D.**
EFFICIENCY OF PLASMAPHORESIS IN PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION OF PATIENTS WITH SEVERE THYROTOXICOSIS.....69
11. **Mardonov B.A., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Rakhmanov K.E.**
COMPLEXITY AND FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTCHOLECYSTECTOMY SYNDROME.....78
12. **Egamberdiyev A.A.**
ENDOVIDEOSURGICAL METHODS FOR THE TREATMENT OF ESOPHAGEAL HIATAL HERNIAS.....84
13. **Abdullayev S.A., Xudoynazarov U.R., Boysariyev Sh.U.**
PROBLEMS OF TREATMENT OF PURULENT-INFLAMMATORY COMPLICATIONS OF SOFT TISSUES IN SINDROME DIABETES MELLITUS FUT.....89

14. **Daminov F.A., Bobokulov A.U.**
PATHOGENETIC ANALYSIS OF GASTRODUODENAL ULCER (LITERATURE REVIEW).....94
15. **Jurayev O.U., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Khursanov Y.E.**
CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE VARICOTROMBOPHLEBITIS AND RESULTS RESEARCH VENOUS SYSTEMS LOWER LIMBS.....101
16. **Shonazarov I.Sh., Oblokulov Z.T.**
THE NATURE OF THE MICROFLORA OF THE ABDOMINAL CAVITY DEPENDING ON THE PH VALUES IN PERFORATED DUODENAL ULCER.....108
17. **Shonazarov I.Sh., Oblokulov Z.T.**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT TACTICS IN PATIENTS WITH PERFORATED DUODENAL ULCER.....113
18. **Raxmatov B.X., Xujabaev S.T.**
CHOICE OF SURGICAL INTERVENTION IN CHRONIC HAEMORRHOIDS.....122
19. **Raxmatov B.X., Xujabaev S.T., Dusiyarov M.M.**
DYNAMICS OF THE WOUND PROCESS AFTER HAEMORRHOIDECTOMY.....126

PEDIATRICS

20. **Garifullina L.M.**
FEATURES OF FORMATION OF RISK FACTORS FOR THE EMERGENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ABDOMINAL OBESITY.....133
21. **Yuldashev B.A., Murodova M.D.**
SUBJECTIVE AND OBJECTIVE CLINICAL SYMPTOMS OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....140
22. **Begnaeva M.U., Siddikov O.U.**
INCIDENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF DRUG POISONING IN CHILDREN.....146
23. **Ulugmuratov A.A.**
EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY FOR INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION IN CHILDREN.....152

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

24. **Ibragimov D.D., Boymuradov Sh.A., Baratova Sh.N.**
INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATING PATIENTS WITH COMBINED INJURIES OF FACIAL BONES WITH ASSESSMENT OF THE HYGIENIC CONDITION OF THE ORAL CAVITY.....156
25. **Islamova N.B.**
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF DENTAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH COMPLETE ADENTIA.....163
26. **Khanazarov D.A.**
ON THE ISSUE OF ODONTOPREPARATION IN ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY.....168

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

27. **Mirdjurayev E.M., Samiyev A.S., Bobomurodov G.A.**
INNOVATIVE METHODOS FOR REHABILITATION OF STROKE COMPLICATIONS.....178
28. **Muzaffarova N.Sh., Shirinov Sh.U.**
THE COURSE OF HEADACHE IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC STROKE.....183

29. **Xudaybergenov N.Y., Kilichev I.A., Adambaev Z.I., Samiyev A.S.**
INFLUENCE OF GEOMAGNETIC ACTIVITY ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF BRAIN STROKES.....188
30. **Sabirov D.M., Eshonov O.Sh., Batirov U.B., Khaydarova S.E.**
MONITORING OF HEMATOLOGICAL INDICES IN PREDICTING OUTCOMES IN CEREBROVASCULAR CRITICAL CONDITIONS.....192
31. **Umirova S.M.**
CORRECTION OF DIABETIC POLYNEUROPATHY NIVALIN WITH PHARMACOPUNCTURE METHOD.....199
32. **Khakimova S.Z.**
REDUCING THE INTENSITY OF COMPLICATIONS WITH THE HELP OF REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH PARKINSON'S DISEASE.....205
33. **Haydarova S. Kh., Sharipov R.Kh., Mavlyanova Z.F., Xudoyqulova F.**
FEATURES OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF LONG-TERM EFFECTS OF PERINATAL LESIONS OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM.....210

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

34. **Lutfullaev U.L., Kobilova Sh.Sh., Safarova N.I., Madaminova N.E.**
PREDICTORS OF CLINICAL OUTCOME IN SENSORINEURAL HEARING LOSS.....219
35. **Lutfullaev U.L., Kobilova Sh.Sh., Safarova N.I., Madaminova N.E., Zoirov O.T., Buronov F.Y., Makhamov Kh.O.**
EFFECTIVENESS OF PROLONGED ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA.....226
36. **Raupova K.M., Nasretdinova M.T.**
PROFESSIONAL HARDNESS OF HEARING UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THE STRONG INTERRUPTED NOISE.....235
37. **Nasretdinova M.T., Xayitov A.A., Dustboboyev D.S., Normurodov N.A.** MANAGEMENT OF OTITIS MEDIA WITH EFFUSION IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES.....241
38. **Nasretdinova M.T., Xayitov A.A., Dustboboyev D.S., Normurodov N.A.**
CHRONIC EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA IN CHILDREN: CYTOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CONFIRMATION OF STAGES OF THE DISEASE.....248
39. **Nasretdinova M.T., Omonova M.Sh.**
MICROFLORA IN CHRONIC POLYPOUS SINUSITIS.....255
40. **Nasretdinova M.T., Omonova M.Sh.**
MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC POLYPOUS RHINOSINUSITIS.....261

ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY

41. **Boyko E.V., Tychiev A.P.**
RESULTS OF TRIMODAL THERAPY FOR INVASIVE BLADDER CANCER.....265
42. **Xamidov O.A.**
CURRENT STATE OF MEDICAL RADIOLOGY IN THE WORLD.....270
43. **Jumanov Z.E., Xamidov O.A., Beknazarova X.N.**
MODERN METHODS OF VISUALIZATION OF GALLBLADDER DISEASES.....295
44. **Raximov N.M, Shaxanova Sh.Sh, Raxmonov K.A.**
S100 PROTEIN EXPRESSION AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE IN DISSEMINATED BREAST CANCER.....302
45. **Urozov N.E., Vypova N.L., Nishanov D.A., Madaliyev A.A., Ibragimov Sh.N., Enikeeva Z.M.**
STUDY OF TOXICOLOGY OF THE ANTITUMOR DRUG KOLKHIPRIT-NEO (K-20).309

46. **Ulmasov F.G., Esankulova B.S.**
IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL STUDY OF THE OVARIAN CANCER
MICROENVIRONMENT AT DIFFERENT STAGES: THE ROLE OF IMMUNE CELLS IN
TUMOR PROGRESSION.....318
47. **Akramov A.R.**
DYNAMICS OF INCIDENCE, AGE AND MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES PRIMARY
BRAIN TUMORS ACCORDING TO THE DATA OF THE SAMARKAND BRANCH
RSSPMC ONCOLOGY AND RADIOLOGY.....322

MORPHOLOGY

48. **Yusupova N.A., Oripov F.S.**
NON-INVASIVE DIAGNOSIS OF FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE GASTRIC UNDER
THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS.....328
49. **Kim T.A., Mavlyanova Z.F., Tastanova G.E.**
INSULIN-PRODUCING FUNCTION OF THE PANCREAS, LIPID PEROXIDATION
INDICATORS AND ANTIOXIDANT DEFENSE SYSTEMS IN RATS EXPOSED TO
LEAD.....336
50. **Zohidova S.H., Mamataliyev A.R.**
MORPHOLOGY OF EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCTS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS
AFTER EXPERIMENTAL REMOVAL OF THE GALLBLADDER.....340
51. **Khamidova F.M., Narzikulov Sh.F.**
MORPHORANGENOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INFLAMMATORY
PROCESSES OF THE RESPIRATORY ORGANS.....346
52. **Davronova M.Sh., Ilyasov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aytimova G.Y.**
INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS ON MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
THE PANCREAS.....358
53. **Khoshimov B.L., Akhmedova S.M.**
INFLUENCE OF METABOLIC SYNDROME ON ARTERIES.....363
54. **Babajanov T.Zh., Ilesov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aitimova G.Y.** IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL
ANALYSIS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES THAT DEVELOPED IN THE TISSUE
STRUCTURES OF THE DUODENUM UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY
DRINKS.....375
55. **Babajanov T.Zh., Ilesov A.S., Avezov A.U., Aitimova G.Y.**
STUDY OF EFFECTS OF ENERGY DRINKS ON MORPHOLOGICAL AND
MORPHOMETRIC STATE OF DUODENAL TISSUE STRUCTURES IN RATS.....381
56. **Kurbanov G.T.**
PECULIARITIES OF THE ORGANIZATION AND STRUCTURE OF THE MAMMALIAN
RESPIRATORY TRACT.....388
57. **Juraev K.D., Islamov Sh.E.**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND PARAMETERS OF THE THYMUS
GLAND IN CHILDREN.....393
58. **Khasanova D.A., Azimova Z.S.**
FEATURES OF LUNG MORPHOLOGY UNDER INFLUENCE OF DYES AND ITS
PHYTCORRECTION.....401
59. **Samieva U. Gulnoza, Rakhmonov T. Sardor.**
PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF IRON DEFICIENCY IN HEART FAILURE.....411

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

60. **Nuritdinov U.A., Fattakhov R.A.**
ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH UNILATERAL ANTERIOR DISCLOSATION OF THE TMJ ARTICULAR DISC.....417

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

61. **Indiaminov S.I., Shoyimov Sh.U., Sagdullayev N.N.**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF HEAD STRUCTURE INJURIES IN PEDESTRIANS INJURED AS A RESULT OF COLLISIONS WITH MOVING VEHICLES.....424

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

62. **Bustanov Sh.Y.**
ETIO-PATHO-MORPHOGENESIS OF COVID-19 (LITERATURE REVIEW).....429
63. **Adjablaeva N. Dinara, Parpieva N. Nargiza**
STRUCTURE OF SOMATIC PATHOLOGY FEATURES OF EPIDEMIOLOGICAL HISTORY DURING THE DEVELOPMENT OF LTBI AND ITS PROGRESSION IN CHILDREN.....438

UROLOGY

64. **Allazov I.S., Allazov S. A.**
CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....447
65. **Allazov S.A., Allazov I.S.**
MODERN VIEWS ON DIAGNOSTIC METHODS AND TREATMENT OF URINARY PERITONITIS.....458

PHARMACOLOGY

66. **Kasimova D.S., Vladimir A.A., Babich S.M., Khamrakulov Sh.Kh.**
CHANGES IN THE DIGESTABILITY OF STARCH DURING INTERACTION WITH FATS IN THE COMPOSITION OF STARCH-FAT SUBSTRATES.....466
67. **Kasimova D.S., Vladimir A.A., Babich S.M., Khamrakulov Sh.Kh.**
INFLUENCE OF FAT HYDROLYSATES ON CHANGES IN THE DIGESTABILITY OF STARCH IN THE COMPOSITION OF STARCH- FAT SUBSTRATES.....474

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ
ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE**JURAYEV Olimjon Usmon ugli**

Assistant

KURBANIYAZOV Zafar Babajanovich

DSc, professor

KHURSANOV Yokubjon Erkin ugli

Assistant

Samarkand State Medical University

CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE VARICOTROMBOPHLEBITIS AND RESULTS RESEARCH VENOUS SYSTEMS LOWER LIMBS

For citation: Jurayev O.U., Kurbaniyazov Z.B., Khursanov Y.E. Clinical characteristics of acute varicotrombophlebitis and results research venous systems lower limbs // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 5, pp.101-107

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14181768>**ANNOTATION**

In basis research laid down analysis results diagnostics And treatments 102 sick With sharp thrombophlebitis of varicose veins of the lower extremities. Acute thrombophlebitis of varicose veins of the lower extremities most often (48.1%) occurs in grade C₃ chronic venous insufficiency according to the CEAP classification and in 46.1% thrombosis was found at the level of the ostial valves. Surgical tactics and the choice of the volume of surgery for OVTF depend on from localizations thrombotic process, according to ultrasound Doppler scanning degrees risk thromboembolic complications And duration diseases.

Key words: Varicose veins of the lower extremities, thrombophlebitis, ultrasound Doppler angioscanning .

ЖУРАЕВ Олимжон Усмон угли**КУРБАНИЯЗОВ Зафар Бабажанович**

DSc, профессор

ХУРСАНОВ Ёкубжон Эркин угли

Ассистент

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

КЛИНИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ОСТРОГО ВАРИКОТРОМБОФЛЕБИТА И РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ВЕНОЗНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ НИЖНИХ КОНЕЧНОСТЕЙ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В основу исследования положен анализ результатов диагностики и лечения 102 больных с острым тромбозом варикозно расширенных вен нижних конечностей. Острый

тромбофлебит варикозно расширенных вен нижних конечностей чаще всего (48,1%) встречается при хронической венозной недостаточности 3 степени по классификации CEAP и в 46,1% тромбоз выявляется на уровне устьевых клапанов. Хирургическая тактика и выбор объема операции при ОВТФ зависят от локализации тромботического процесса, данных ультразвуковой доплерографии, степени риска тромбоэмболических осложнений и длительности заболевания.

Ключевые слова: Варикозно расширенные вены нижних конечностей, тромбофлебит, ультразвуковая доплерография, ангиосканирование.

JURAEV Olimjon Usmon ugli

Assistent

KURBANIYaZOV Zafar Babajanovich

DSc, professor

XURSANOV Yokubjon Erkin ugli

Assistent

Samarkandskiy gosudarstvennyy meditsinskiy universitet

O'TKIR VARIKOTROMBOFLEBITLARNING KLINIK XARAKTERISTIKASI VA VENA TIZIMLARINI TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqotlar asosida 102 bemor oyoq varikoz tomirlarining o'tkir tromboflebiti bilan diagnostika va davolash natijalari tahlil qilindi. Pastki oyoq varikoz tomirlarining o'tkir tromboflebiti ko'pincha (48,1%) CEAP tasnifiga ko'ra C 3-darajali surunkali venoz etishmovchilikda uchraydi va 46,1% da ostial klapanlar darajasida tromboz aniqlangan. Jarrohlik taktikasi va O'VTF uchun operatsiya hajmini tanlash trombotik jarayonning lokalizatsiyasiga bog'liq, ultratovushli Doppler tekshiruviga ko'ra, tromboembolik asoratlar xavfi va kasalliklarning davomiyligi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pastki oyoq varikoz kengayishi, tromboflebit, ultratovush Doppler-angioskanerlash.

Relevance. Acute varic thrombophlebitis (AVTP) continues to be the most common often encountered urgent vascular disease, frequency whom By to some data reaches to 17.2%.

The disease most often develops in patients of working age. age, What does given problem more more current V plan social and labor rehabilitation. The ratio of damage to large andsmall subcutaneous veins varic thrombophlebitis is 9:1.

The most dangerous variant of the course of OVTF is the ascending one. varic thrombophlebitis , at which thrombotic process has a tendency to spread in the proximal direction. In this case, due to the smaller diameter of the great saphenous vein, compared to common femoral, the top of the thrombus in most cases remains not fixed, What creates real threat For development thrombosis deep veins (DVT) And thromboembolism pulmonary arteries (TELA) .

So, By to some data, DVT at OVTF meets V 8.4% cases, at this to 40% patients as a result combined thrombosis superficial And deep veins become deep disabled people . Most heavy outcome combined thrombosis is blue phlegmasia (venous gangrene), which occurs in 1.5% sick.

The aim of the study is to determine efficiency ultrasonic duplex scanning V diagnostics And choice surgical treatment method acute thrombophlebitis of varicose veins of the lower extremities.

Material and research methods. IN basis research laid down analysis results diagnostics And treatments 102 sick With sharp thrombophlebitis of varicose veins of the lower extremities, who were in the surgery department from 2018 to 2023 vessels multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University.

Among the patients there are female faces gender compiled 77 (65.6%), male – 25 (24.5%). Age sick hesitated from 18 to 71 years, on average composing 31.4±6.7 year .

According to classification SEAR at patients the following were available stages CVI (table. 1).

Table 1
Distribution of patients depending on the degree of chronicity venous insufficiency by classification SEAR

Degree CVI	Clinical manifestations	Quantity patients	
		abs .	%
C2	Varicose extended subcutaneous veins	31	29.8
C3	Edema	49	48.1
C4	Pigmentation and/or venous eczema; lipodermatosclerosis	17	16.6
C5	All the above skin changes + healed venous trophic ulcer	5	4.9

U majority patients (n=80) initial stages of CVI were noted. At the same time, 4.9% of patients with OVTF developed in the background healed venous trophic ulcer.

Duration existence varicose diseases lower limbs varied from 3 years to 17 years.

From general numbers sick right-hand localization varicothrombophlebitis was observed at 43 (42.2%) patients, left-sided 57 (55.8%) patients. More at 2 (1.9%) patients was observed double-sided process. U 4 patients had recurrent development of OVTF, i.e. after 2-6 months after thrombophlebitis. Three of these patients had a history of By about OVTF big subcutaneous veins was done only crossectomy V different medicinal institutions, without subsequent observations.

Localization And prevalence thrombotic process determined V in accordance With classification F. Verrel et al . (1998), according to which everyone patients were distributed next way:

I type (n=40) - thrombotic process Not reached ostial valves of the great or small saphenous veins, while the distribution thrombus on deep veins were absent;

- type (n=47) - the proximal part of the thrombosis was at the level ostial valves;
- type (n=4) - spreading thrombosis on deep venoussystem through saphenofemoral And saphenopopliteal anastomosis;

- type (n=2) - spreading thrombotic process on deep venous system through insufficient extended perforating veins.

It was found that out of 77 female patients who applied,gender 5.5 % accepted hormonal contraceptives, 12.2% were pregnant V terms from 3 to 8 months. Overweight bodies there was at 26 (25.5%) from them.

Deadlines admission patients from beginning manifestations clinical signs varicothrombophlebitis varied from 1 to 17 days, V average amounting to 4.1±0.9 days .

Most of the patients (55.1%) were admitted to hospital on the 4th or more day from the onset of the disease and only 44.9% from they were hospitalized on time to 3 days.

Spreading thrombotic process V areas hips Andshins depending on the duration of the disease are given in the following table (table. 2).

Table 2
Localization thrombotic process V depending on its terms

Localization thrombotic process	Limitation thrombotic process (day)				Total	
	1 - 2	3 - 4	5 - 6	> 7		
Shin	3	1/1 *	2	1/1 *	9	
Hip	Lower third	7	4	2	2	15
	Average third	11	7	4	3	25
	Upper third	20	17	7	3	47
Transition V deep	1	2	2	1	6	

veins

Note: * - small subcutaneous vein

Results and discussion. Upon examination, all patients had thrombosed varicose extended veins systems big or subcutaneous veins, which manifested itself in the form of cord-like compaction and pain in the veins (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Thrombosed varicose extended subcutaneous veins medial surfaces right shins (5 days from beginning of the process)

Fig. 2. Thrombosed varicose extended veins medial surfaces shins on background healed venous trophic ulcers (7 day from the beginning process)

U 11 (10.8%) sick was celebrated total thrombosis of all dilated subcutaneous veins, including the posterior and lateral venous nodes.

Localization thrombotic process on the lower leg was observed in 9 patients; in two cases, the great saphenous vein was affected, in 15 cases - the small subcutaneous veins. Varicothrombophlebitis big subcutaneous veins And her tributaries at the level of the thigh, was the most frequent localization of signs which is marked at 93 sick.

Table 3

Localization acute varicothrombophlebitis By on the move big and small subcutaneous veins

Localization thrombotic process		n = 102
Shin		2/ 7 *
Hip	lower third	15
	average third	25
	top third	47
Transition V deep veins	through saphenopopliteal anastomosis	1
	through saphenofemoral anastomosis	3
	through perforating veins shins	2

Note: * Defeat small subcutaneous veins

U 6 from these patients It was noted transition thrombotic process into the deep venous system, in 4 of which it was localized in femoroiliac segment, at 2 popliteal -femoral segment (table 3).

In 5 patients, OVTF developed against the background of healed venous trophic ulcer, which worsened the course of the ulcer process (Fig. 2).

Indicators frequencies the development of OVTF ranged from 12 to 15, averaging 16.3 cases per year. How showed results research Not there are trend To decrease development OVTF V latest 5 years, and V 2023 year their frequency increased V 1.5 times.

When analyzing the results of ultrasound examination, the presence of thrombus V clearance subcutaneous vein.

Localization thrombotic process at the level of the lower leg was detected in 9 patients, at the level of the hip in 87 patients. At the same time, 6 patients had transition of the thrombotic process into the deep venous system through saphenofemoral (n=3) or saphenopopliteal (n=1) junction or through the system of perforating veins of the leg (n=2) (Fig. 3), causing a picture acute thrombosis deep veins With more expressed clinical symptoms.

Fig. 3. UZDAS. Distribution thrombus through saphenofemoral fistulas (arrow indicated thrombus tip)

Fig. 4. UZDAS. Visualized total thrombosis varicose extended veins medial surface shins

Us was carried out comparative grade proximal border venous thrombotic process, installed clinical methods And By data UZDAS (table 4).

IN most cases length thrombotic process, revealed on basis UZDAS, was some more By comparison such determined on basis clinical data. Thus, if the average length of the thrombotic process on the veins of the lower leg, identified on the basis of clinical data amounted to 31.2±4.5 cm, then the same figure, revealed with the help of ultrasound, was 38.4±5.1 cm. Necessary note, What such reliable indicators were also identified when determining the boundaries of the thrombotic process on thigh. The average length of the thrombotic process on the thigh is determined clinically compiled 32.6±5.3 cm, A at help UZDAS 52.3±7.1 cm (p<0.05).

It should be noted that 6 (5.9%) patients showed ultrasound imaging total thrombosis of all dilated subcutaneous veins, including the posterior and lateral venous nodes (Fig. 4).

Table 4

Comparative grade results UZDAS With clinical data

Localization thrombotic process	UZDAS	R
---------------------------------	-------	---

		Clinically		
Shin		9	9	>0.05
Hip	Lower third	15	12	<0.05
	Average third	25	22	<0.05
	Upper third	47	51	<0.05
Transition to the deep veins		6	6	>0.05

Note: p – reliability differences

Based on the results of using the ultrasound imaging, the topographic and anatomical localization of the thrombotic process in the superficial and deep venous systems, on which further treatment tactics depended, was clarified. In this regard, in the diagnosis of OVTF, the leading role should be given to ultrasound imaging, which provides sufficient information on the state of the superficial and deep veins along their entire length, the prevalence of the thrombotic process, the nature of the apical part of the thrombus, the presence of fluid accumulation in the paravasal space, and the asymptomatic transition of the thrombus to the deep venous system, which is almost impossible to establish based on the clinical manifestations of the disease.

Conclusions.

- In diagnosing OVTF, the leading role should be given to ultrasound imaging, which provides sufficient information about the state of the superficial and deep veins along their entire length, the prevalence of the thrombotic process, and the nature of the apical part of the thrombus.
- Acute thrombophlebitis of varicose veins of the lower extremities most often (48.1%) occurs in grade C₃ chronic venous insufficiency according to the CEAP classification, and in 46.1% thrombosis was found at the level of the ostial valves.
- Surgical tactics and the choice of the volume of surgery for OVTF depend from localizations thrombotic process, according to ultrasound Doppler scanning degrees risk thromboembolic complications And duration diseases.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. 21st World Congress of the International Union of Angiology, May 22-26, Rome, Italy) // Phlebology. Special issue. - 2014. - №46. - 115 p. (in Eng).
2. Belcaro G., Casarone M.R., Di Renzo A., Drandolini R. et al. Foam sclerotherapy, surgery sclerotherapy, and combined treatment for varicose veins: a 10 year, prospective randomized, controlled, trial (VEDICO trial). // Angiology. - 2020. - Vol. 54, №3.- P. 307-315(in Eng).
3. Beresford T., Smith J.J., Brown L., Greenhalgh R.M. et al. A comparison of health related quality of life of patients with primary and recurrent varicose veins. // Phlebology.- 2019. - Vol. 18, № 1. - P. 35-37. (in Eng).
4. Cabrera Garrido J.R., Cabrera Garcia Olmedo J.R., Garcia Olmedo Dominguez M.A. Elargissement des limites de la schlerotherapie: nouveaux produits sclerosants. // Phlebologie. - 1997. - Vol. 50. - P. 181-188. (in Eng).
5. Danielsson G. What is the role of incompetent perforator veins in chronic venous disease? G. Danielsson, B. Eklof, R L. Kistner. // Phlebology. - 2014. -Vol. 1.-P. 67-71. (in Eng).
6. Evans CJ, Fowkes FG, Ruckley CV, Lee AJ. Prevalence of varicose veins and chronic venous insufficiency in men and women in the general population: Edinburgh Vein Study. // J Epidemiol Community Health. - 2018. - Vol.53. - P. 149-153. (in Eng).
7. Grass JD, Hiemer W. Bypass procedures for venous obstruction. In: Raju S, Villavicencio JL, editors. Surgical management of venous disease. // 1st ed. Baltimore: Williams & Wilkins. - 2020. - P. 289-305. (in Eng).
8. Hurst DR, Forauer AR, Bloom JR, Greenfield LJ, Wakefield TW, Williams DM. Diagnosis and endovascular treatment of iliocaaval compression syndrome. // J Vase Surg. - 2021. - Vol. 34. - P. 106-13. (in Eng).

9. Isakulov , sh. R., Rizaev , f. A. (2022). Craniofacial zharohatlarda tibby yordamni tashkillashtirishni takimillashtirish va davolash usullarini yaxshilashga zamonaviy Jondaszow . Journal of Biomedicine and Practice, 7(1). 2022. – T. 7. – No. 1.
10. Kahn SR, Ginsberg JS. Relationship between deep venous thrombosis and the postthrombotic syndrome. //Arch Intern Med. - 2018. - Vol. 164,- P. 17—(in Eng).
11. Lin S-D., Lin T-M., Lee S-S., Yang Y-L. et al. Endoscopeassisted management primary varicose veins below the knee. // Phlebology. - 2016. - Vol. 20, №4.-P. 163-169 (in Eng).
12. Marston W.A., Owens L.V., Davies s. et al. Endovenous saphenous ablation corrects the hemodynamic abnormality in patients with CEAP clinical clfss 3-6 CVI due to superficial reflux. // Vase. Endovascular Surg. - 2017. - Vol. 40, №1 (in Eng).
13. Neglen P, Thrasher TL, Raju S. Venous outflow obstruction: an underestimated contributor to chronic venous disease. // J Vase Surg. - 2014. - Vol.38. - P. 879-885. (in Eng).
14. Pierik EG, Van Urk H, Hop WC, Wittens CH. Endoscopic versus open subfascial division of incompetent perforating veins in the treatment of venous leg ulceration: a randomized trial // J. Vase. Surg. - 2015. - Vol. 26. - P. 1049- 1054. (in Eng).
15. Tisi P.V., Beverley C., Rees A. Injection sclerotherapy for varicose veins. // Cochrane Database Syst Rev. -2018,- Vol. 18, №4.-CD001732. (in Eng).
16. Tursunov O. M. et al. Interventional percutaneous technologies in the treatment of patients with obstructive jaundice syndrome // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. – 2022. – T. 7. – No. 1
17. Venkatraman P.D., Anand S.C, Dean C., Nettleton R. et al. Pilot study investigating the feasibility of an ulcerspecific quality of life questionnaire. //Phlebology..- 2018,- Vol.20,№ 1,- P. 14-27. (in Eng).
18. Zacur H, Kirsner RS. Debridement: rationale and therapeutic options Wounds. // Labropoulos N, Leon M, Nicolaides AN.-2020.- Vol. 14,- P.2E-7E. (in Eng).
19. Poseryaev A. et al. TREATMENT OF VARICOTROMBOFLEBITIS AT THE PRESENT STAGE //MEDICAL SCIENCES. – 2020. – C. 40. (in Eng).

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 5

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000